

MULTIPLE-CHOICE AND SHORT ANSWER QUESTIONS IN LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT: THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN ITEM FORMAT AND SECOND LANGUAGE READING

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Abstract: *This article identifies the notion of reading comprehension and reading skill in an English language and presents the important information about the implementation of various strategies and techniques in the process of teaching English language to schoolchildren and some of English language level learners. Moreover, this paper mentions the significance of language assessment and the usage of various kinds of questions in the process of language evaluation. In particular, multiple-choice questions and short answer questions are given as a vivid testple of language assessment means in terms of reading skill evaluation. In addition to this, the article emphasizes the interplay between item format and second language reading process.*

Keywords: *reading skill, reading comprehension, English language teaching, methodology, language assessment, language evaluation, format, ESL, learners, multiple choice questions, short answer questions.*

Introduction

In 2013, the British Council estimated that 750 million people globally spoke English as a foreign language (EFL) and 350 million spoke English as a second language (ESL). That's almost one billion English speakers, or roughly one out of every seven people on the planet. Educators and test makers are attempting to produce better instruction and more effective evaluation of learners' English competency in response to the constantly rising population of English learners. Thus, Reading comprehension is one of the basic skills necessary for one to communicate successfully in a foreign language, in particular English language. At the same time, reading skill is considered to be an indispensable part of various language level testing tests on international and domestic levels. For instance, International English language testing system (also known as IELTS) includes the reading comprehension test into the overall testination as a part of four sections. Therefore, it is vital to identify the methodological characteristics of teaching English language reading comprehension, or second language reading skill in general. Especially in language assessment process, the correct usage of question types identifies the effectiveness of evaluation rate and probability of assessing the learners constructively. Based on this precondition, a teaching approach with the implementation of multiple choice questions and short answer questions is adopted in this study to testify whether this approach suits the English language learners with comparative low English proficiency, and whether it can be popularized to the educational organizations and in English language classroom respectively.

Literature review. The article's findings to be integrated into teaching-learning process were taken from numerous articles and books on English language reading skill development and language assessment means materials. Among articles, there are research papers of Cervetti, G.

N., Hiebert, E. H. "The sixth pillar of reading instruction: Knowledge development" published in 2015 in *The Reading Teacher* journal. In addition to this, the empirical research "An Empirical Study of the Effects of Reading-writing Connection on Non-English Majors' Writing Performance" on reading and writing skills' findings authored by Feifei Wang, *Theory and Practice in Language Studies* 2020 were taken into account while writing this research paper.

Methods & Materials. The following article implies the quantitative and qualitative research methods in order to find out the peculiarities of interplay between item format and English language learning in context of the reading skill. Through triangulation, researchers can improve the legitimacy of a study using mixed methodologies.

Triangulation is a strategy for researchers to seek verification and convergence of findings from many methodologies used to investigate the same issue, while accounting for each approach's possible biases. The main phenomena investigated in this study was how the aforesaid formats affect English learners' reading in numerous domains, including performance, metacognitive awareness, task completion processes, and task perceptions. The quantitative data primarily focused on the association between metacognitive awareness (reading awareness) and test performance in multiple choices and short answer question forms, as well as the differences in the results of various reading tests. The qualitative strand supported the findings by paying close attention to participants' test results in regard to the data.

Results & Discussion

Reading comprehension is one of the most difficult human activities to master. Reading theorists have struggled with how to express reading comprehension in a complete and meaningful way, and many various theoretical models have been presented in recent decades (McNamara & Magliano, 2009; Perfetti & Stafura, 2014). Models of particular comprehension processes span from broad theoretical models describing linkages and interactions among comprehension subcomponents to models of individual comprehension processes.

Word reading ability, working memory, inference creation, comprehension monitoring, vocabulary, and prior knowledge are only a few of the linguistic and cognitive processes that go into reading comprehension. Component models that address subcomponents of comprehension reflect the varied character of reading comprehension.

However, linguists later argued that the nature of language relies on its context, so it is unnatural to divide language into discrete elements and measure them separately. A historical review of language assessment methods can provide test creators with information on language competency tests in certain circumstances. Post-structuralist language theories led to limited production test forms during the integrative era (e.g., cloze, short-answer question, dictation, etc.). These tests essentially ask test takers to develop written replies based on their comprehension of a reading. Although these test approaches might more successfully measure language, they still provided an imperfect picture of students' communication ability. Extended production test formats (i.e., essays and oral interviews) became popular for assessing productive skills during the communicative era in response to an increased focus on interpersonal communication because they allowed test-takers to demonstrate their communication processes in more authentic contexts.

In terms of the question types discussed in the current paper, some instructors may favor multiple choice questions over short answer questions in classroom assessments, especially in big classes, which is a regular occurrence in English language courses in several parts of the world, such as Asia. For big classrooms, there are three key reasons why teachers may favor

MCQs over SAQs. For starters, multiple choice question items are simple to score since scoring computers can assess them quickly and cheaply. However, because scoring includes skilled human labour, the scoring procedure for short answer questions can be time consuming and costly. Second, because each MCQ has pre-determined answers, teachers and raters simply require the answer key to grade them. For multiple choice question tests, inter-rater reliability is not an issue. Short response questions, on the other hand, demand test takers to express their ideas in words or phrases, making it difficult for evaluators to reach a high level of agreement (inter-rater reliability).

Language testing has argued that because MCQ test-takers rely on selective deletion (or, in other words, eliminating prescribed options via text clues) and micro-level reading strategies (for testple, deducing the meaning of unfamiliar words, extracting information by searching the text), generalizing multiple choice question test scores for overall proficiency is difficult.

Furthermore, the possibility of random guessing may affect the reliability and validity of MCQ testinations. Because the right answer is hidden inside a collection of predetermined possibilities, it's possible that test-takers may guess at random when they're stumped. The style of SA questions, on the other hand, should decrease the test-taking technique of random guessing since they compel test-takers to utilize the target language to build their replies, which produces a high degree of authenticity. Short answer questions allow test takers to apply a number of reading methods, including as discerning literal and inferred meanings, inferring information that is not clearly stated, and acquiring the primary concept by linking hints from multiple phrases, according to researchers. According to these researches, SA questions may be more useful in determining test takers' reading ability.

While reliability and validity are important test assessment criteria, test authors must evaluate how closely a test of L2 reading corresponds to the nature of the reading process. A foundation for understanding how readers engage with texts is provided by five broad reading processes and two common reading approaches. Scanning, skimming, reading to learn, reading to integrate, and reading to assess, criticize, and utilize are the five main reading objectives that explain how readers engage with texts. Scanning and skimming are widely used by readers to find specific information or rapidly grasp the essence of a text.

When it comes to the empirical findings, it's worth noting that while quantitative studies demonstrated that using metacognitive strategies did not improve reading test performance, qualitative analyses suggested that strategy use may have a favorable impact on test-takers' reading comprehension. There was no interaction effect between the test format and the degree of metacognitive awareness, indicating that the degrees of metacognitive awareness created by multiple choice questions and short response questions were equivalent. However, the researcher discovered that the tactics used to complete MC and SA questions had an influence on not only the participants' test completion order, but also their reading comprehension. The majority of participants stated that they read the paragraph first and then completed the text.

Based on the previous findings, the researchers observed that participants employed micro- and macro-level tactics to decode particular information and extract the overall concept of the source texts. Participants concentrated on analyzing the meaning of words, finding significant information, and taking notes on the reading content, for example, when reading the texts. Participants would scan the texts to get the idea or preview subheadings to make predictions about the reading to help them understand it better. Participants used the comprehension monitoring approach rereading to increase their grasp of the texts or to explain their misunderstanding about the texts, in addition to micro- and macro-level strategies. Because SA

questions were more demanding in terms of written response formulation than MC questions, some participants stated that SA questions needed more frequent rereading than MC questions. Because of the complexity of the questions, test takers were more inclined to reread the texts for SA questions than MC ones. Participants reported employing test-wiseness methods to assist build their responses when completing MC and SA reading questions.

Conclusion

Summarizing the current study's findings and those of other writers, it can be stated that there was no beneficial association between reading test performance and the degree of metacognitive awareness induced by strategy usage frequency. Correlation studies revealed whether the participants' English reading competence was more essential than their strategy utilization. Although using strategies often did not improve test performance, strategies for multiple choice and short answer questions were shown to promote interactive processes that allowed participants to get a better knowledge of the source texts. In addition, participants' opinions, as well as a mix of both, demonstrated positive and negative connections between test structure, reading comprehension, and language learning. As a result, while assessing English reading proficiency, participants' test format preferences should be taken into account. The employment of diverse test formats in L2 reading courses has pedagogical ramifications, according to this study.

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